

Binder effect on CeO₂-based technical catalyst performance: insights and implications

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ABSTRACT

Cerium oxide has earned recognition as a valuable support material in heterogeneous catalysis due to its exceptional catalytic properties. Ensuring the mechanical stability of CeO₂-based technical catalysts is crucial for reliable industrial performance. This study reports two primary approaches for enhancing the mechanical resistance of these catalysts. Firstly, thermal treatment was explored, applying various calcination temperatures and heating rates, which highlighted the balance between mechanical strength and porosity in catalyst supports. Secondly, the influence of inorganic binders –boehmite, bentonite, and kaolinite– on the physicochemical properties and catalytic performance of CeO₂-based supports in the context of CO₂ methanation was systematically evaluated. Binder-modified CeO₂-based technical supports (with a CeO₂-to-binder ratio of 10:1) were fabricated, impregnated with nickel salts, characterized using N₂-physisorption, compression assays, XRD, TGA, SEM-EDX, and H₂-TPR, and their activity in the methanation of CO₂ was assessed. Bentonite demonstrated remarkable strength enhancement, doubling the mechanical resistance compared to the pure CeO₂ support. However, employing clay-altered supports as catalysts led to unfavorable results for application in practical cases. Boehmite emerged as a highly promising binder, demonstrating exceptional chemical and mechanical stability and minimal disruption to the activity of the catalyst in CO₂ methanation thus establishing its practical suitability for catalyst development. This research highlights the nuanced influence of different binders on catalyst performance, providing valuable insights into the design and optimization of CeO₂-based catalysts for applied catalytic technologies.

1. Introduction

Cerium(IV) oxide (CeO₂) has proven to be a highly effective support in heterogeneous catalysis. Its remarkable catalytic performance is attributed to several key factors, including oxygen mobility, redox properties, outstanding thermal and structural stability [1]. It has been therefore widely used as support in catalytic reactions like treatment of exhaust gases, hydrogenation of alkynes, methanol oxidation, water-gas shift reaction [2], CO₂ methanation [3] or fuel cells [4]; in combination with transition metal and/or metal oxides [5,6]; or even as active catalyst alone in some specific reactions as hydrochloric acid oxidation [7] or dry reforming [8]. CeO₂ powders can be tailored for practical applications using diverse shaping methods, including injection molding, tape-casting, die pressing, extrusion, and advanced 3D-printing technologies [9–12]. Among them, extrusion allows high throughput at relatively low costs.

There are critical physical attributes of CeO₂-based materials, such as their comparatively lower specific surface areas and insufficient mechanical resistance to be implemented in real catalytic reactors [10]. Ensuring a certain level of CeO₂-based catalyst strength in order to avoid fracture under the weight of the catalytic bed or fluid forces is essential to maintain smooth catalyst performance and prevent operational issues as blockage, pressure drop, uneven flow or downstream fouling [13,14]. In general, solid porous materials are fragile, and therefore, the mechanical strength is one of the key parameters for the reliable and efficient performance of an industrial catalyst [15]. However, most scientific studies tend to prioritize the active phase behavior over the mechanical strength of technical catalysts. This limited focus on mechanical properties can be attributed to the complexity of understanding the interactions between multiple components when shaped into practical geometries [16].

Sintering, a common thermal process involving high temperatures,

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represents a viable strategy for producing mechanically resistant structures through interparticle atomic diffusion in detriment to material porosity [12,17]; for instance, ceramic electrolytes for solid oxide fuel cell applications [18]. Beyond thermal treatment, inorganic binders are oftentimes used to increase the mechanical strength of catalytic supports in extruded materials [16]. In this aspect, a combination of inorganic binders and mild temperature treatments [19] could be employed without compromising the original porous structures.

Boehmite is commonly used as inorganic binder in, for instance, extrusion of alumina mixtures [20]. Prabhakaran et al. presented a novel approach for fabricating high-density, near-net-shape alumina ceramics using gel casting with boehmite as an inorganic binder [21]. They observed that the addition of boehmite (10 wt%) in the alumina slurry adjusted the fluidity for gel casting. Indeed, extrusion of boehmite can be used to directly produce alumina supports with high performance in biodiesel production [22]. Incorporating boehmite as a binder was essential for achieving stable sulfated zirconia extrudates [23]. Peptizing boehmite particles in an acidic medium improved the interaction between zirconia and aluminum hydroxides, thereby enhancing the mechanical resistance of the catalysts. Peptized boehmite also demonstrated strong binding potential when combined with zeolite at a 70:30 ratio, enhancing support strength by a factor of 5 in comparison to the pure zeolite extrudate [24].

Other inorganic binders are found throughout the support preparation industry. Bentonite and kaolinite proved to be effective binders for shaping and strengthening Mg-Al mixed oxide catalysts, making the extrudates 9 times more resistant than when SiO₂ or γ -Al₂O₃ were used as binders [25]. Hernando et al. used bentonite and attapulgite to increase the resistance of zeolite-supported ZrO₂ technical catalysts for biomass pyrolysis, and observed the binders effect was not innocent on the catalysts activity [26].

Intensive research on catalyst shaping has surged in recent years due to a recognized need to bring novel scientific catalytic formulations closer to industrial applications, particularly concerning various binder types and additives. Nevertheless, the utilization of CeO₂-based catalysts, renowned for their exceptional activity in specific catalytic applications, remains an unexplored area of research. Therefore, in this work we study the impact of thermal treatment and the use of three distinct inorganic binders on the performance of CeO₂-based technical catalysts in the CO₂ methanation reaction, with the aim of enabling their potential application in industrial reactors.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Cerium(III) nitrate hexahydrate, [Ce(NO₃)₃·6 H₂O] (99.5%, Alfa Aesar) was used for the synthesis of supports. Methylcellulose (M_w ~ 14,000, Sigma) was used as plasticizer. Bentonite (Alfa Aesar), boehmite (Sasol) and kaolinite (Sigma-Aldrich) were used as binders. Nickel (II) nitrate hexahydrate [Ni(NO₃)₂·6 H₂O] (98%, Alfa Aesar) was used as metal precursor.

2.2. Catalyst preparation

CeO₂ particles were synthesized by the calcination of Ce(NO₃)₃·6 H₂O for 5 h at 500 °C (1 °C·min⁻¹). The solid obtained was then ball milled using a Retsch MM400 Oscillating mill. CeO₂ supports were prepared as described elsewhere [10], dried at 105 °C and calcined (500, 600 or 800 °C) for 4 h (0.5 – 10 °C·min⁻¹). For binder-modified CeO₂ supports, a paste was formed by mixing the CeO₂ particles, the binder (bentonite or kaolinite), methylcellulose (10:1:0.55 dry mass ratio) and a predetermined volume of an aqueous 0.1 mM HNO₃ solution using a Thinky Are-250 Conditioning Planetary Mixer. Similarly, a paste composed of CeO₂, boehmite, and methylcellulose (in a ratio of 10:1:0.65) and a sample with reduced boehmite content (10:0.5:0.65)

were prepared using the same procedure. The pastes were extruded using a Caleva Multi-Lab Extruder (1 mm diameter die, 55 rpm), and the extruded cylinders were processed in a Caleva Multi-Lab Spheronizer (10 – 30 min, 2000 rpm). The resulting pellets were dried at 80 °C for 12 h and calcined at 500 °C for 4 h (1 °C·min⁻¹).

The supports were impregnated with Ni(NO₃)₂·6 H₂O by incipient wetness impregnation, aiming at a Ni nominal content of 10 wt%. In a typical synthesis, 0.825 g of Ni(NO₃)₂·6 H₂O were dissolved in deionized water and the precursor solution was then drop-casted over 1.5 g of CeO₂ catalyst supports. The impregnated spheres were air-dried at atmospheric conditions for 4 h, desiccated at 80 °C for 12 h and calcined at 500 °C for 1 h (2 °C·min⁻¹). The reduced form of the catalyst was achieved by reduction under a hydrogen atmosphere (5% H₂ and 95% Ar, 100 mL·min⁻¹) at 350 °C for 3 h (1 °C·min⁻¹).

2.3. Characterization

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images and elemental composition of the samples were acquired using a Zeiss Auriga 60 field emission scanning electron microscope equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometer (Oxford X-Max). For Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) elemental analysis and mapping, the non-reduced technical catalysts were embedded in epoxy resin and allowed to cure for 24 h. Subsequently, the specimens were polished to expose the cross-section of the spheres and then coated by gold sputtering. The chemical composition was determined by averaging five measurements taken across the sphere's radius.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were collected using a Bruker D8 Advance A25 diffractometer within the 2 θ range of 20–80°. The XRD analysis used Cu K α radiation with a wavelength of 1.5406 Å, a voltage of 40 kV, a current of 40 mA, and a step size of 0.02° (2 s per step).

The average crystal sizes of Ni⁰ and CeO₂ were estimated using Scherrer's equation at 2 θ = 44.50° for Ni(111) and 2 θ = 47.36° for CeO₂ (220): $D = (K\lambda/\beta\cos\theta)$, where λ is the X-ray wavelength, β is the full width of the diffraction line at half-maximum (FWHM), and θ is the Bragg angle.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) were performed from room temperature to 700 °C (1 °C·min⁻¹) under air flow (20 mL·min⁻¹) on a Setaram SensysEVO TG DSC apparatus.

N₂-physisorption measurements were performed at liquid nitrogen temperature using a TriStar II 3020-Micromeritics analyzer. Before the measurements, the samples underwent degassing under N₂ flow at 90 °C for 1 h and then at 250 °C overnight in a FlowPrep 060-Micromeritics instrument. The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method was applied to calculate the BET surface area within a relative pressure (P/P⁰) range of 0.05–0.3. The average pore size was determined using the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method applied to the desorption branch of the isotherms. The total pore volume was obtained from the maximum adsorption value at P/P⁰ = 0.997. 100 mg of sample were used for each measurement.

Temperature-programmed reduction (H₂-TPR) measurements were carried out in an AutoChem (Micromeritics) instrument using 12 vol% H₂/Ar at a flow rate of 50 NmL·min⁻¹. The temperature range was set from 35 °C to 800 °C with a heating ramp of 10 °C·min⁻¹. The amount of H₂ uptake was measured using a thermal conductivity detector, and 100 mg of sample were used for each measurement.

The compression strength of the materials was determined using a Zwick-Roell universal testing machine with a load cell of 200 N. The reported results are an average of 20 measurements.

2.4. Catalytic tests

Catalyst testing was conducted using a fixed-bed catalytic reactor with dimensions of 13 mm internal diameter and 305 mm length (Microactivity Reference from PID Eng&Tech). In each experiment, 0.3

g of dry catalyst pellets were used. To maintain uniform temperature across the catalyst bed, the catalyst was mixed with 3 g of Al_2O_3 spheres ($d_p = 1$ mm, Norpro Saint Gobain). Temperature monitoring was achieved by placing a K-type thermocouple at the midpoint of the diluted catalyst bed.

Prior to the experiments, catalysts were in-situ reduced at 350 °C for 3 h ($1\text{ °C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) under a flow of H_2 at 100 N mL $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, followed by cooling to 50 °C using the same ramp. Subsequent experiments were carried out under a stoichiometric molar ratio of 4 for H_2/CO_2 (supplied by Linde). The operating conditions included a pressure of 5 bar.g and gas flow rates (F) ranging from 100 to 300 mL $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

The catalyst screening was performed within a temperature range of 250–350 °C, at intervals of 25 °C, starting from the lowest temperature. Following the reaction, the product stream was directed through a cold liquid-gas separator at 5 °C, which effectively trapped water, allowing for measurement of the dry flow via a mass flow meter (MF, Bronkhorst).

The composition of the dry gas was determined with an on-line gas micro-chromatograph (490 microGC, Agilent Technologies) calibrated for CH_4 , H_2 , CO , CO_2 and C_2H_6 . Three measures were taken at each temperature, and the results have a relative error of the 2%.

Stability experiments were conducted at a fixed temperature of 300 °C, a pressure of 5 bar.g and $F = 200$ N mL $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, and the product composition was measured every hour during 90 h.

The CO_2 conversion (χ_{CO_2}) was calculated following Eq. 1, where F_{CH_4} , F_{CO} and F_{CO_2} represent the molar flow rate of CH_4 , CO and CO_2 in the outlet gas.

$$\chi_{\text{CO}_2}(\%) = \left(\frac{F_{\text{CH}_4} + F_{\text{CO}}}{F_{\text{CO}_2} + F_{\text{CH}_4} + F_{\text{CO}}} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

The activity of the catalysts was calculated through Eq. 2,

$$\text{activity} = \frac{\chi_{\text{CO}_2 t}}{\chi_{\text{CO}_2 t_0}} \quad (2)$$

where $\chi_{\text{CO}_2 t}$ is the CO_2 conversion at time t and $\chi_{\text{CO}_2 t_0}$ is the CO_2 conversion at 0 h.

3. Results

3.1. Thermal treatment effects

A first approach involved the evaluation of different calcination conditions to enhance the mechanical resistance of the CeO_2 -based supports (Fig. 1). The increase of calcination temperature led to a sharp increase in the mechanical resistance of the materials. At a calcination temperature of 600 °C, the resistance to compression of the support increased from 2 to 6 N, while at 800 °C, a significantly higher value of

11 N was achieved. However, it was observed that the specific surface areas corresponding to these results were considerably lower than the reference value, particularly for the sample calcined at 800 °C, which practically lost its entire surface area (Fig. S1). Results indicated that interparticle atomic diffusion was facilitated by applying elevated temperatures during calcination of the green bodies, resulting in strengthened interparticle bonds and the formation of a more compact and denser structure. As a result, the porous structure collapsed which led to a decrease in the material's specific surface area and an increase of the average pore diameter from 12 nm to 19 nm. Published studies have shown that mechanical strength is improved through structural densification, resulting in a decreased surface area and an enlarged pore size distribution [27]. Striking a balance between mechanical strength and porosity became essential to optimize the overall performance of the supports.

To avoid the significant loss of surface area, a milder heating ramp was employed during the calcination process. By maintaining the same calcination temperature, 500 °C, while using gentler heating ramps, 0.5 and 1 °C $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, the resistance to compression nearly doubled, while preserving the original surface area and the average pore diameter of the CeO_2 supports. In contrast, applying a 10 °C $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ ramp resulted in compression resistance and porosity similar to those achieved with a 5 °C $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ ramp. Throughout the calcination process, the organic plasticizer and residual acidic water are released through combustion and evaporation, respectively. Employing a slow heating ramp seems an effective strategy for the gradual release of these components, thereby minimizing structural defects [28] and maintaining the integrity of the CeO_2 -based supports.

3.2. Impact of inorganic binders

A second approach to reinforce the structure of the CeO_2 pellets is the use of inorganic binders. To assess their impact on the mechanical resistance of CeO_2 -based pellets, three distinct inorganic binders, namely bentonite (bn), kaolinite (kn), and boehmite (bh), were examined. In this experimental set, the binders were incorporated into the formulation at a 10:1 ratio (ceria:binder, w/w), and the resulting structures, CeO_2 -bn, CeO_2 -kn, and CeO_2 -bh, were subjected to calcination at 500 °C with a 1 °C $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ ramp, based on the results detailed in the previous section.

3.2.1. Characterization of binder-modified pellets

The morphology analysis of the synthesized CeO_2 supports was conducted using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). As depicted in Fig. 2, all the pellets, regardless of the binder type, exhibited smooth surfaces and a spherical shape, indicating a uniform and compact

Fig. 1. Effect of the calcination temperature (left) and heating ramp (right) on the surface area and the mechanical resistance of CeO_2 pellets.

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of CeO₂-bn (left), CeO₂-kn (middle) and CeO₂-bh (right). Scalebar is 1 mm.

structure. There were no observable traces of powder detachment, further validating the effectiveness of the shaping process. The mean diameters of the CeO₂ supports are presented in Table 1, revealing that all spheres achieved diameters close to that of the extrusion die (1 mm) following spheronization.

Table 1 summarizes the porosity and mechanical properties of CeO₂-based supports. Notably, the addition of boehmite and bentonite to the pellets led to a significant increase in surface area ($\sim 73 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$), compared to pure CeO₂ and kaolinite-modified pellets ($60\text{--}64 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$). Particularly for CeO₂-bh, the remarkable rise in surface area can be attributed to the binder's exceptional surface area of $268.4 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ (see Table S1). In the case of CeO₂-bn, where bentonite, although not inherently highly porous ($51.3 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$), is used as a binder, the supports still exhibited a noticeable increase in surface area. The generalized increase is primarily attributed to the loss of water molecules and hydroxyl groups during the calcination process, which leads to the formation of additional pores within the supports structure, consequently enhancing their overall porosity. A similar, although less pronounced, effect is noticeable with CeO₂-kn. In this case, the binder has a very low surface area of $9.6 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ and is essentially non-porous, which would typically reduce the overall porosity of the support. However, the evaporation of water molecules during the process mitigates this reduction, resulting in a surface area that is more closely aligned with that of pure CeO₂ Fig. 3.

The mechanical resistance of the CeO₂ spheres in the absence of binder and calcined under optimized conditions exhibited a compression strength of 4 N (Table S3). All the three materials incorporating inorganic binders exhibited an increase in mechanical resistance. Among them, upon addition of boehmite or kaolinite this resistance was slightly increased to 5 N. Notably, bentonite doubled the resistance of the CeO₂-based spheres. To gain insight into potential mechanisms affecting the structural integrity of the pellets, the calcination process of the CeO₂-based green bodies was investigated through thermogravimetric analysis.

Fig. 4 shows the TGA-DSC profiles of the CeO₂-based green bodies and the corresponding binder powders. The first weight loss is observed at 100 °C, more pronounced in CeO₂-bh and CeO₂-bn, attributed to dehydration of physically adsorbed surface water. The calcination of the methylcellulose plasticizer occurred at around 230 °C for all the support materials, contributing to a weight loss of approximately 5%. The thermal behavior of CeO₂ powder, as illustrated in Fig. S3, exhibits

comparatively mild thermal transitions, indicative of its inherent stability within the experimental conditions. As a result, any thermal phenomena observed below the calcination temperature of 500 °C in the support materials are attributed to the binder and methylcellulose components. This includes the exothermic calcination of methylcellulose and the binder-associated endothermic processes, all of which take place either at or below the temperature required for the support's calcination.

DSC analysis of the bentonite binder revealed an initial endothermic process indicative of the removal of physisorbed water molecules, after which a progressive weight loss occurred starting at 300 °C up to 675 °C, attributed to the sequential processes of water removal and dehydroxylation of the clay [29]. The calcination of CeO₂-bn green bodies causes the reversible dehydration of both physisorbed and interlayer water within the clay, followed by its subsequent partial dihydroxylation. During thermal treatment of kaolinite powder, TGA analysis indicated two endothermic processes. The first, of low intensity, involves minor weight loss due to hydration water elimination without structural changes. A subsequent endothermic peak at 450 °C correlates with kaolinite dehydroxylation, a process that leads to the formation of the metastable metakaolin phase [30,31] and whose completion is observed within the temperature range spanning from 450 °C to 600 °C. At 500 °C, the dehydroxylation of the kaolinite binder in CeO₂-kn results in a 0.80% weight loss. This indicates that post-calcination, the support spheres will comprise a mixture of CeO₂, the dehydroxylated and reactive metakaolin phase, and residual non-dehydroxylated kaolinite.

As for the CeO₂-bh calcination, following the removal of physically adsorbed water and methylcellulose plasticizer, a weight loss of approximately 0.85% occurred in the 300–500 °C range. This gradual, endothermic process corresponds to the conversion of boehmite, AlO(OH), into $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ [32]. The TGA profile of the pristine boehmite binder confirmed the completion of this transformation at the calcination temperature of 500 °C.

Significantly, these binder-related processes—namely the dehydration of bentonite, dehydroxylation of kaolinite, and the boehmite-to-alumina transition—lead to water evaporation which, in turn, might generate additional porosity within the CeO₂-based structures, in line with the findings from N₂-adsorption measurements.

The introduction of inorganic binders—bentonite, kaolinite, and boehmite—impacted on the mechanical properties and porosity of CeO₂-based pellets. Mechanical tests revealed a significant enhancement

Table 1
Physico-chemical properties of the shaped CeO₂-based supports and catalysts.

	Mean diameter (mm)	S _{BET} (m ² ·g ⁻¹)	Pore size (nm)	Compression strength (N)		S _{BET} (m ² ·g ⁻¹)	Pore size (nm)	Compression strength (N)
CeO ₂	1.3 ± 0.3	62.4	11.5	4 ± 1	NiO-CeO ₂	44.8	12.0	6 ± 3
CeO ₂ -bn	1.3 ± 0.2	72.5	8.9	8 ± 2	NiO-CeO ₂ -bn	52.7	9.6	9 ± 3
CeO ₂ -bh	1.4 ± 0.1	73.2	10.5	5 ± 1	NiO-CeO ₂ -bh	59.5	10.2	8 ± 4
CeO ₂ -kn	1.4 ± 0.2	64.2	10.6	5 ± 1	NiO-CeO ₂ -kn	49.7	10.6	6 ± 2

Fig. 3. N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms (left) and BJH Desorption dA/dlog(D) Pore Area as a function of pore diameter (right) of the CeO₂-based supports.

Fig. 4. TGA profiles of (left) CeO₂-bh, (middle) CeO₂-bn, (right) CeO₂-kn, and the corresponding binder powders.

in compression strength, particularly a twofold increase when using bentonite, compared to the initial CeO₂ supports. Thermal analyses revealed binder-associated processes that contribute to water evaporation and potential increase in surface area. These results highlight the role of binders in shaping both the structural integrity and properties of CeO₂-based pellets.

3.2.2. Catalyst characterization

The synthesis of NiO-CeO₂-based catalysts, namely NiO-CeO₂-bh, NiO-CeO₂-bn, and NiO-CeO₂-kn, was accomplished through the incipient wetness impregnation technique followed by subsequent calcination steps. Unfortunately, this procedural sequence led to the fragmentation of the initial spherical structures, as exemplified in Fig. S5. The extent of this rupture was more pronounced in the spheres containing clay binders, NiO-CeO₂-bn and NiO-CeO₂-kn, exhibiting a fracture of approximately 20% of the catalyst mass, while the NiO-CeO₂-bh spheres experienced a comparatively lower degree of rupture at around 12%.

The increased structural fragility upon impregnation observed in the clay binder-containing structures can be attributed to the unique properties inherent to these materials. Bentonite's interlayer spaces undergo expansion upon exposure to water, which is subsequently evaporated during the calcination process, thereby exerting stress on the pellet structure [33]. While kaolinite is known for its low swelling capacity, there is limited information available about its swelling behavior after

transformation into metakaolin. Furthermore, previous studies have reported the adsorption of Ni²⁺ by clay minerals [34]. The substantial cation adsorption capacity of these clays can result in the incorporation of Ni²⁺ ions into their interlamellar spaces and the subsequent growth of Ni²⁺ into NiO particles during calcination within these spaces may also contribute to structural collapse.

After the incorporation of the active phase, surface and mechanical properties were modified, as displayed in Table 1. S_{BET} decreased between 10 and 20 m²·g⁻¹ in comparison to the surface area of non-impregnated supports. The isotherms indicate reduced surface area and pore volume, with no significant alteration in shape observed in the isotherms of the support and the catalyst, suggesting the preservation of the pore structure (see Fig. S2) [35]. The occupation of the pores by nickel oxide resulted in a reinforcement of the structure, leading to an increase in the compression strength of all the spheres. Notably, the NiO-CeO₂-bh catalyst displayed comparable resistance to the bentonite-modified material, while maintaining a higher surface area. The elevated support resistance post-impregnation with the active metal facilitates the implementation of CeO₂-based catalysts in a fixed-bed reactor, mitigating the risks of operational breakage.

XRD analysis on the reduced catalyst samples showed the typical peaks of metallic Ni and CeO₂ phase. The peaks of the binders could not be identified in the diffractogram of the corresponding catalyst (Fig. S4). The crystallite sizes of Ni and CeO₂ particles were estimated by Scherrer's equation, using the peaks at 2θ = 44.7° and 2θ = 47.6°. The

average crystallite size of Ni in Ni-CeO₂-bn and Ni-CeO₂-kn were estimated at 16.7 and 17.6 nm, respectively. The Ni peak of the Ni-CeO₂-bh didn't allow for estimation of the Ni crystallite size, although by the size and broadness of the peak it suggests small Ni crystallites.

The cross-section of the spheres prior to reduction was analyzed by EDX analysis to determine the distribution of the binders and the Ni within the CeO₂-based structure (Figs. S7-S9). The quantification of Ni, Ce, Al, and Si elements across the radial axis of the spheres revealed an elevated Ni content at the periphery while maintaining relative homogeneity in the rest of areas. The average Ni wt% percentages for the NiO-CeO₂-bn and NiO-CeO₂-kn catalysts closely approximated the nominal values, at 9.6% and 9.8%, respectively, based on five measured points. NiO-CeO₂-bh exhibited a more heterogeneous distribution of Ni, with elevated Ni concentrations (31.9%) particularly aligning with regions displaying heightened Al content, in contrast to other segments of the material, where an average of 9.6% Ni was estimated.

An insufficient dispersion of the boehmite binder within the structure was evidenced in the EDX mapping images, where Al-rich aggregates ranging from 5 to 40 μm are visible throughout the sphere cross-section (Fig. 5). Previous studies have also documented difficulties in achieving a uniform dispersion of the boehmite when used as binder in zeolite-based structures [24,36]. These results infer that a complete homogeneous dispersion of the boehmite binder through the structure of CeO₂-bh was not achieved despite the high energy mixing conditions of the paste and the peptization of the particles with HNO₃. Besides, Ni is especially concentrated in regions where substantial Al₂O₃ agglomerates are identified, showing a greater affinity with the alumina phase than with the ceria phase, a factor that may influence the catalyst's physicochemical properties.

Fig. 6 shows the results of the H₂-TPR measurements conducted on the catalyst samples. The unmodified Ni-CeO₂ catalyst displayed two peaks below 250 °C, assigned to the reduction of surface oxygen species related to the incorporation of Ni²⁺ ions into the CeO₂ lattice. Additionally, a pronounced peak centered at 290 °C corresponding to the reduction of NiO species in weak interaction with the CeO₂ surface [37, 38].

Upon incorporation of clay binders, namely bentonite and kaolinite, alterations in the reduction behavior of NiO became evident. The reduction peaks of Ni-CeO₂-bn and Ni-CeO₂-kn broadened and shifted to higher temperatures, notably centered at 350 °C. Clay minerals have complex compositions and the diverse oxides within the clay interact with NiO to various extents, as suggested by the broadening of the peak compared to that of pure CeO₂. The interaction of NiO with clay surfaces resulted in higher reduction temperatures likely associated to NiO in the

Fig. 6. H₂-TPR profiles of the catalysts. Ni-CeO₂ data was published in [10].

outer surfaces of the clay [39,40]. Reduction peaks attributed to NiO within the clay's interlamellar sites, which typically occur at higher temperatures (>550°C), were not detected [41].

Of particular interest is the Ni-CeO₂-bh catalyst which exhibited the highest reduction temperature among the studied catalysts. This increase in reduction temperature can be rationalized by the emergence of nickel phases that exhibit heightened interaction with the Al₂O₃-modified catalyst support. This interaction is further substantiated by EDX images, which revealed the preferential affinity of Ni species for alumina clusters. The presence of a distinct shoulder above 400 °C in the reduction profile is consistent with the presence of NiO species moderately interacting with Al₂O₃ [42], further confirming the influence of the modified catalyst's composition on its reduction behavior. The reduction of nickel aluminate species, which may originate from the interaction between Ni and the binder, is not readily observable due to the simultaneous reduction of bulk CeO₂ initiating at 650 °C.

While bentonite initially exhibited higher structural cohesion in non-impregnated supports, it proved less suitable for wet impregnation methods. Interestingly, the differences in mechanical resistance among the binders were mitigated upon NiO particle impregnation. Furthermore, the variations in textural properties and reduction profiles of the catalysts underscore the distinct effects of different binders on the morphology, dispersion, and reducibility of the active phase, offering valuable insights for catalyst design and optimization and reactor implementation.

3.2.3. Influence of binder content

Considering our findings regarding the impact of various binders on NiO-CeO₂-based catalysts, the focus shifted to the study of boehmite as a

Fig. 5. EDX elemental mapping images of the NiO-CeO₂-bh catalyst cross-section.

binder to refine the catalyst performance. To this end, the CeO₂-to-boehmite ratio was adjusted to 10:0.5, yielding the CeO₂-0.5bh support.

SEM characterization of the CeO₂-0.5bh support revealed a smooth surface and a spherical form, maintaining a mean diameter of 1.3 ± 0.1 μm (Fig. S6). In comparison to the CeO₂-bh counterpart, the surface area of CeO₂-0.5bh registered a slight reduction, $68.1 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, positioning it between the pure CeO₂ support and the CeO₂-bh analogue, which validates the direct association between the heightened porosity of the boehmite-modified CeO₂ supports and the presence of alumina in the material. Impregnation of the support with Ni species and subsequent calcination led to a notable reduction in structural breakage, decreasing from 12% to 4% when compared to CeO₂-bh, thus linking this phenomenon to the presence of the binder in the CeO₂ matrix.

Both CeO₂-0.5bh and NiO-CeO₂-0.5bh, 4 and 6 N respectively, did not demonstrate a notable improvement in mechanical strength when compared to the pure CeO₂ shaped support or the impregnated NiO-CeO₂-bh, which indicated that the reduced boehmite content within the CeO₂-based carriers is not sufficient to achieve enhancement in the catalyst strength.

3.2.4. Catalytic performance

The effect of the different binders on the activity of the methanation catalysts was addressed. For that purpose, the catalytic activity of the Ni-CeO₂-bh, Ni-CeO₂-bn and Ni-CeO₂-kn catalysts was examined in the temperature range between 250 and 350 °C (Fig. 7).

At the temperatures tested, the Ni-CeO₂-bh catalysts demonstrated similar conversion levels to those obtained with Ni over pure CeO₂ supports. The catalysts containing clay binders, however, exhibited significantly lower CO₂ conversions, with differences of up to 17% at lower temperatures and 9% at the highest temperature measured. Among the materials essayed, the bentonite-containing catalyst exhibited the poorest CO₂ conversions. Generally, CeO₂ is recognized as one of the most effective catalyst support for Ni in the process of CO₂ methanation, ahead of alumina [43,44], silica [45,46] and various other oxides, in terms of catalytic activity. The addition of aluminosilicate surfaces like bentonite and kaolinite to the CeO₂ support clays negatively impacted the activity of the catalysts in the methanation reaction. However, even though Al₂O₃ inherently exhibits lower methanation activity compared to CeO₂, its integration into the support significantly

enhanced the support's surface area. This compensatory effect resulted in CO₂ conversion levels comparable to those of the pure support, as evidenced by the performance of the Ni-CeO₂-bh catalyst.

Modifying the boehmite ratio from 10:1 to 10:0.5 in the CeO₂ supports did not yield any discernible benefits regarding catalyst activity, implying that a binder ratio as high as 10:1 does not adversely affect the catalyst's activity compared to lower binder quantities or pure CeO₂ supports.

During the 90-hour stability tests conducted on the three catalysts, it was observed that the Ni-CeO₂-bn catalyst experienced the most significant decline in activity over time, reaching 90% of its initial activity by the end of the test period. Both the Ni-CeO₂-kn and Ni-CeO₂-bh catalysts demonstrated greater resilience, retaining 95% and 96% of their initial activity, respectively, upon completion of the test.

Screening experiments exploring the impact of various binders on CeO₂-based methanation catalysts singled out boehmite as the most promising among the studied options. Boehmite exhibited exceptional mechanical and chemical stability while sustaining catalytic methanation activity at levels comparable to pure CeO₂ supports, demonstrating its potential for widespread utilization in catalytic processes. Considering the results obtained, boehmite stands out as a compatible binder with CeO₂, positioning it as a robust candidate for catalytic applications that require both stability and high performance.

4. Conclusions

This study has examined two primary strategies to enhance the mechanical resistance of CeO₂-based technical catalysts. The first approach involved thermal treatment, where a range of temperatures and heating rates were investigated revealing the delicate balance between mechanical strength and porosity in the catalyst supports. The use of mild heating ramps was preferable for maintaining porosity while increasing mechanical strength.

The second approach focused on the use of inorganic binders, namely boehmite, bentonite, and kaolinite, and the evaluation of their influence on the physicochemical properties of the catalyst supports, revealing the complex interplay between binders, mechanical characteristics, and catalytic activity, and providing insights into the multifaceted nature of these interactions.

Fig. 7. CO₂ conversion (%) of Ni-CeO₂, Ni-CeO₂-bn, Ni-CeO₂-kn, Ni-CeO₂-bh and Ni-CeO₂-0.5bh catalysts as a function of reaction temperature at constant flow F = 200 N mL·min⁻¹ (left) and stability tests at T = 300 °C (right). Ni-CeO₂ data was published in [10]. P = 5 bar·g, m_{cat} = 0.3 g, and H₂/CO₂ molar ratio = 4.

The findings highlighted the significant influence of binder selection on various aspects of the catalyst, including its textural properties, reducibility, compatibility with wet impregnation methods, and catalytic activity in CO₂ methanation. Among the tested binders, bentonite provided superior mechanical strength, exhibiting a twofold increase compared to the pure CeO₂ support, while boehmite and kaolinite had weak impact on the support's compression strength. However, when the clay-modified supports were impregnated with Ni species and used as catalysts, it resulted in notable fracture of the CeO₂-based supports and a loss of catalytic activity during the methanation reaction experiments, properties that make them unsuitable for large-scale industrial use. Boehmite, however, emerged as a promising binder option, displaying stability, minimal interference with catalytic methanation activity, and a reduction in catalyst breakage during impregnation and calcination. These characteristics render boehmite a compatible binder for CeO₂-based technical catalysts, making it a practical choice for catalyst development.

This study bridges the gap between fundamental catalyst science and practical industrial applications, offering a pathway to enhance the performance of CeO₂-based technical catalysts in CO₂ methanation and potentially other catalytic processes. These findings may facilitate the design and optimization of more efficient and resistant catalytic materials to tackle applied catalytic challenges.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Elena Martín Conceptualization, Visualization and Writing – original draft. Kandela Ruiz Investigation. Albert Llorente Investigation. Martí Biset Resources. Jordi Guilera Writing - Review & Editing and Project Administration.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.cattod.2023.114473](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2023.114473).

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